

Corrosion of 3Y-TZP ceramics for dental applications

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ABSTRACT

Due to its excellent properties 3Y-TZP ceramic is a suitable material for various applications, including dental materials for implants or crowns. One of the advantages of this material is its non-metallic nature, which is important for patients allergic to metals, including titanium [1]. However, the long-term surface stability of this material in a humid environment is still a matter of concern and may limit its application [2]. Additionally, the oral environment is very diverse and the surface of dental materials is exposed to different pH ranges, which could be highly acidic because of consumption of food and beverages, and conditions associated with reflux of gastric fluid [3]. Apart from the change of pH, substantial temperature fluctuations occur in the oral cavity.

The aim of this work was to study the long-term corrosion behavior of commercial and non-commercial 3Y-TZP ceramics in acidic environment and the influence of the loss of ions stabilizing tetragonal zirconia on tetragonal-to-monoclinic phase transformation of zirconia. This work also attempts to answer the question whether acid-related corrosion is a process, which is, by its nature and mechanism, different from low-temperature degradation (LTD). In addition, the influence of the loss of tetragonal zirconia stabilizing ions (Y^{3+}) on sensitivity of studied materials to LTD was also studied. Two commercial materials were tested: zirconia-based dental materials stabilized in their tetragonal form by addition of yttrium (3Y-TZP) – IVOCLAR IPS e.max[®] ZirCAD and DOCERAM Nacera[®]. In addition, non-commercial 3Y-TZP ceramics have been prepared from a zirconia powder stabilized by the addition of 3 mol% of yttria and synthesized by hydrothermal process. Green bodies prepared by axial pressing of granulated powder at 50 MPa in a steel die were sintered for 2 h at 1450°C (3Y-TZP-1450) or 1500°C (3Y-TZP-1500). Sintered and polished ceramics have been corroded in 4% acetic acid at three different temperatures (37°C, 60°C, 80°C) with maximum duration of the test: 31 days (IVOCLAR and DOCERAM) and 40 days (ceramics prepared in our laboratory). For DOCERAM and IVOCLAR the corrosion tests at 37°C and 60°C were extended, respectively up to 265 days and 130 days. The kinetics of LTD was evaluated by performing the Accelerating Aging Test (AAT) in water steam at 134°C, under the pressure of 2 bars. It has been postulated [4], that 1 h in an autoclave under these conditions roughly corresponds to 1-4 years in-vivo at 37°C. Corrosion and aging effects, expressed in terms of the amount of monoclinic zirconia formed at the material's surface as the result of phase transformation of tetragonal zirconia, were monitored with the use of the X-ray powder diffractometer Panalytical Empyrean with Bragg-Brentano geometry at a range of $2\Theta = 10^\circ - 80^\circ$ using $CuK\alpha$ radiation with a wavelength of 0.15405 nm. To monitor the amount of leached ions from the materials during the corrosion tests chemical analysis of corrosion media was carried out using the mass spectrometry in inductively coupled plasma (ICP – MS, Agilent 7900).

Acidic corrosion of 3Y-TZP dental ceramics was associated with leaching of stabilizing ions from zirconia ceramics. Depletion of yttrium ions increased with temperature (Table 1.). In the case of 3Y-TZP-1450, the highest observed amount of leached yttrium represents almost 30% of all the content of yttrium in this material. Measurable phase transformation was observed already after 40 days at 37°C: no monoclinic zirconia was detected under these conditions in other tested materials. Significant increase of the monoclinic phase content in DOCERAM, IVOCLAR and 3Y-TZP-1500 was observed only after exposure of the materials to corrosive medium at 80°C. The least corrosion resistant commercial and non-commercial materials, i.e. IVOCLAR and 3Y-TZP-1450 were tested also in deionized water, as a reference medium. While the transformation rate was similar to that obtained

during the corrosion in 4% acetic acid, the acidic environment accelerated depletion of yttrium ions to the solution and was more aggressive than deionized water (Table 1).

The kinetics of tetragonal to monoclinic phase transformation was described by the Mehl-Avrami-Johnson (JAM) equation [5]. Calculated activation energies of tetragonal to monoclinic phase transformation for IVOCLAR, 3Y-TZP-1450 and 3Y-TZP-1500 were respectively calculated as follows: 78.72 ± 0.01 kJ/mol, 65.00 ± 6.06 kJ/mol and 92.60 ± 18.38 kJ/mol. Fig. 1 shows the time dependencies of experimental (from corrosion tests in acetic acid) and calculated monoclinic phase contents at various temperatures ranging from 37°C to 134°C, respectively for 3Y-TZP-1450 (Fig. 1. a)) 3Y-TZP-1500 (Fig.1 b)) and IVOCLAR (Fig.1 c)). The actual content of the monoclinic phase in the initial stages of the experiment was in all cases slightly lower than the calculated ones. However, at longer exposure to corrosive media, the measured and calculated data overlap. The expected time to transform to more than 80% of monoclinic phase in the tested materials at 37°C can be then estimated as follows: IVOCLAR: 7 years, 3Y-TZP-1450: 1 year, 3Y-TZP-1500: 18 years. However, the transformation of the 3Y-TZP-1500 could be overestimated, due to the high standard deviation of the activation energy. For DOCERAM, no kinetics for lower temperatures were measured and the predicted transformation could not be calculated. The collected data from this study indicated that there was no significant impact of depletion of the stabilizing yttrium ions on phase transformation in tested commercial materials and the material 3Y-TZP-1500 prepared in our laboratory. The transformation, which occurs after corrosion at temperatures higher than 37°C, was correlated with nucleation and growth processes. The calculated activation energies are comparable to those obtained by other authors [6], [7].

Table 1. Normalized amount of yttrium ions leached out from tested materials in different aqueous solutions; duration of the experiment for commercial materials was 31 days and for non-commercial materials, 40 days.

Temperature of the experiment	IVOCLAR		DOCERAM	3Y-TZP-1450		3Y-TZP-1500
	4% acetic acid $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	Water $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	4% acetic acid $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	4% acetic acid mg/cm^2	Water $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	4% acetic acid $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$
37°C	4.2 ± 0.7	-	1.3 ± 0.5	0.16 ± 0.19	-	8.9 ± 2.1
60°C	6.9 ± 0.4	-	2.2 ± 0.5	0.57 ± 0.1	-	7.9 ± 0.9
80°C	8.7 ± 0.1	3.8 ± 1.5	3.2 ± 1.5	9.9 ± 0.2	92.4 ± 14.7	24.8 ± 0.7

Fig. 1. Relationship between the amount of monoclinic phase and aging time at various temperatures: comparison of measured data with the values estimated from the MAJ equation: solid dots represent experimental data, empty dots are the values calculated from the MAJ equation: a) 3Y-TZP-1450, b) 3Y-TZP-1500, c) IVOCLAR

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